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ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAINS: EXPLORING PROBIOTIC PROPERTIES IN VEGETABLE PRODUCTS

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Abstract

This article undertakes a comprehensive synthesis of select vegetable products indigenous to the mountainous regions of Romania, specifically focusing on onion (*Allium cepa*) and the natural juices derived from apples (*Malus pumila*) and pears (*Pyrus communis*). The primary objective of this investigation is to underscore that these products, characterized by their elevated nutritional profiles and inherent probiotic properties, constitute staples widely utilized in Romania. Entrepreneurs situated in the Romanian mountainous regions, specializing in vegetable products, accentuate the pivotal role of these items in their commercial enterprises. The preliminary insights for this study were extracted from the official websites of mountain producers, while the statistical data were sourced from the Romanian National Register of Mountain Products.

Keywords: mountain entrepreneurs, natural probiotic, vegetable products

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M.C. – conceptualization; B.C. – conceptualization and final

The *Allium cepa*, commonly known as onion and classified under plant products by OECD (2019), exhibits a round or elongated shape and is available in white, red, or yellow varieties. Onions are versatile, existing in fresh, dried, semi-dried, or green forms. Fruit juice, categorized as a vegetable product by FAO (2005), is characterized as an unfermented yet fermentable liquid derived from the edible portion of ripe and fresh fruit, or fruit preserved in a healthy state, even post-harvest, through treatments compliant with Codex Alimentarius Commission regulations.

In Romania, *Allium cepa*, particularly in its green or dried forms, stands out as the most consumed variant, with 56 mountain producers documented in the Romanian National Register of Mountain Products (RNPM) as of September 21, 2021. A regional breakdown reveals representation from various counties, including Argeş, Cluj, Hunedoara, Mureş, and Timiş, each contributing one producer. Additionally, Bacău, Caraş, Sibiu, and Suceava have two producers each, while Gorj and Satu Mare host three producers. Notably, Maramureş boasts seven producers, Vâlcea has nine, and Covasna leads with 18. Out of the 329 mountain producers specializing in probiotic plant products, 56 are dedicated to onions, constituting a substantial 17.02% share within this entrepreneur class.

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Figure 1. Mountain producers and related assortments of *allium cepa* (onions) from Romania

Source: National Agency for Mountain Areas (2021), National Register of Mountain Products

Natural juices, specifically those derived from apples (*Malus pumila*) and pears (*Pyrus communis*), serve as an apt medium for incorporating *Lactobacillus paracasei* as a probiotic, as highlighted in research by Pimentel et al. (2015). Over the storage period, studies indicate a notable increase in the viable cell count in apples due to their sucrose content. Notably, unfermented juice experienced a higher loss of ascorbic acid (40%) compared to fermented juice (23%). This trend was consistent for antioxidant activity and polyphenolic compounds, endowing the functional Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2021)

food with enhanced nutritional benefits (Pereira et al., 2013). Apple juice, when subjected to fermentation with *Lactobacillus plantarum* PCS26, results in a functional beverage characterized by high sensory acceptance and a promising shelf life (Dimitrovski, 2015). Meanwhile, Changchong pear juice demonstrated efficacy in promoting growth and enhancing survival for the *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* ST-III strain and other probiotic representatives of this species, as demonstrated by Yan et al. (2021).

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The escalating demand for functional foods and probiotics surpasses that of traditional dairy products, prompting continuous efforts in product development. Panda et al.'s (2017) study, centered on the preparation technology and characteristics of lactic acid-fermented juice using prick pear (*Opuntia* sp.), underscores this trend. Moreover, research findings indicate that *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* GG, sourced from pears, exhibits the capability to control the growth of *Salmonella* and *L. monocytogenes* on freshly cut pears (Iglesias et al., 2017).

As per the Romanian National Register of Mountain Products (RNPM) dated September 21, 2021, natural apple (SM) and pear (SP) juices, originating from 11 producers, are available in the market. These include two producers from Caraş-Severin specializing in pear juice, and eight

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producers from Caraş-Severin, Bacău, Dâmboviţa, Harghita, Maramureş, Sibiu, Vâlcea, each contributing to the apple juice category. Additionally, one producer from Caraş-Severin offers a mix of apple and pear juice (SMP). Notably, among the 329 mountain producers of vegetable products, only 11 are engaged in the production of apple and pear juice, constituting a modest 3.34% of the total.

Figure 3.5. Mountain producers of apple and pear juices from Romania

Source: National Agency for Mountain Areas (2021), National Register of Mountain Products

The prevalence of allium cepa (onion) and apple/pear juices among the overall producers and assortments of mountain products in Romania remains modest. In contrast, numerous European countries beyond Central and Eastern Europe, as well as other global nations, exhibit significantly

higher proportions in the production and consumption of onion/apple/pear juices. To foster the growth of the plant sector, particularly focusing on potent natural probiotics like *allium sativum* (garlic), as well as apple and pear juices, it is imperative for both public and private governance in Romania to enact essential measures.

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PROJECTION OF DEMOGRAPHIC TRENDS IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN BUSINESS LANDSCAPE ACROSS THE SECONDARY, TERTIARY, AND QUATERNARY SECTORS

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Abstract

The demographic landscape of active enterprises in the Romanian population holds significant potential for the overall economic development of both the country and Europe at large. The presented data indicates a positive improvement in the business demography of Romania, particularly in the context of increased employment opportunities within newly established enterprises. This paper aims to provide a forecast for the demographic trends in mountain businesses, specifically focusing on the secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sectors. The analysis encompasses projections that contribute to understanding the evolving dynamics of the business landscape in the mountainous regions.

Keywords: mountain business demography, population of active enterprise, forecast

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The imperative for equitable development, aiming to mitigate regional disparities and support less developed countries, was acknowledged in the preamble of the Treaty of Rome in 1957. This treaty also emphasized the promotion of employment and enhanced labor mobility within the Community. A scrutiny of Romania's key macroeconomic indicators reveals that, more than a decade post its EU accession, the country has experienced both the reduction and exacerbation of existing disparities. (Ceaurescu, 2018)

Eurostat data on business demography in mountain entrepreneurship in Romania (excluding agricultural businesses) over the period 2008-2018, particularly in the context of forecasts, manifests variations, prompting a comprehensive analysis. This forecast analysis, coupled with self-correlation analysis, identifies similarities in forecasted observations contingent upon statistical analysis gaps (Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021a-e).

The prognosticated values for the active enterprise population in secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sub-sectors indicate a significant investment focus on the mountainous regions of Romania. Whether through non-reimbursable/reimbursable funds or self-financing mechanisms, the trajectory of mountain entrepreneurship is anticipated to flourish predominantly in the tertiary and quaternary sectors, aligned with the primary sector.

Table 1. The structure of business demography from Romanian mountain for secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors

Year/Indices	I1	I2	I3	I4	I5	I6	I7	I8	I9	I10	I11	I12
2008	166.823	23.926	16.986	16.011	1.265	1.284.229	1.249.353	51.825	43.389	35.560	27.792	74.616
2009	161.131	14.248	28.955	13.181	553	1.130.471	1.096.497	31.967	25.891	49.922	38.769	55.042
2010	144.988	11.498		13.256	832	1.065.478	1.035.313	37.398	32.659			50.873
2011	223.436	27.931	37.692	16.757	251	1.193.044	1.088.489	51.089	33.603	45.430	13.362	52.028
2012	242.464	28.438	14.128	16.396	414	1.234.239	1.108.817	58.065	39.843	30.047	23.484	45.906
2013	246.416	54.785	39.386	13.183	433	1.228.381	1.094.456	83.114	35.159	45.955	13.165	49.956
2014	249.931	23.355	18.864	14.535	417	1.235.524	1.091.701	47.799	34.361	26.850	18.491	41.409
2015	250.856	28.613	21.223	15.179	427	1.237.507	1.093.175	48.456	29.903	29.036	12.862	47.392
2016	259.915	26.915	21.307	25.925	499	1.333.250	1.149.066	45.747	27.422	28.178	12.509	69.618
2017	268.422	30.330	20.587	14.042	472	1.343.469	1.170.353	49.122	31.191	34.212	16.786	50.805
2018	275.467	30.652		18.573	413	1.328.165	1.182.500	47.938	30.020			50.105
2018/2008	65,1	28,1	21,2	16,0	-67,4	3,4	-5,4	-7,5	-30,8	-3,8	-39,6	-32,8

Year/Indices	I13	I14	I15	I16	I17	I18	I19	I20	I21	I22	I23	I24	I25	I26	I27

2008	41.322		24,52	14,34	10,18		9,6	4,04	2,17	83,72	2,77	2,09	80,57	5,81	
2009	35.724	-3,41	26,81	8,84	17,97		8,18	2,83	2,24	80,99	4,42	1,72	54,08	4,87	
2010	34.287	-10,02		7,93			9,14	3,51	3,25	87,33			48,37	4,77	
2011	34.889	54,11	29,37	12,5	16,87	70,04	7,5	4,28	1,83	65,77	3,81	1,21	49,12	4,36	1,46
2012	28.577	8,52	17,56	11,73	5,83	115,08	6,76	4,7	2,04	68,62	2,43	2,13	60,64	3,72	2,39
2013	33.282	1,63	38,22	22,23	15,98	114,65	5,35	6,77	1,52	42,3	3,74	1,17	50,1	4,07	2,52
2014	29.112	1,43	16,89	9,34	7,55	52,04	5,82	3,87	2,05	71,89	2,17	1,42	42,24	3,35	2,46
2015	29.683	0,37	19,87	11,41	8,46	53,38	6,05	3,92	1,69	61,71	2,35	1,37	59,66	3,83	2,52
2016	43.839	3,61	18,55	10,36	8,2	47,32	9,97	3,43	1,7	59,94	2,11	1,32	58,8	5,22	2,87
2017	32.222	3,27	18,97	11,3	7,67	60,12	5,23	3,66	1,62	63,5	2,55	1,66	57,67	3,78	2,72
2018	33.703	2,62		11,13		64,91	6,74	3,61	1,56	62,62			48,67	3,77	2,37
2018/2008	-18,4	-176,8	-22,6	-22,4	-24,7	-7,3	-	-	-28,1	-25,2	-7,9	-20,6	-39,6	-	62,3
							29,8	10,6						35,1	

Source: Author according to Eurostat - Business Demography Statistics

Evident in Figures 1 (Predictions for Romania's mountain entrepreneurship in 2028 across discussed sectors) and 2 (Forecasts for mountain entrepreneurship regarding the residual autocorrelation function), the sub-sectors poised for substantial development in Romania encompass Industry (excluding construction), Constructions, Transport and storage, Arts, entertainment and recreation, other service activities, Accommodation and food services, Information and communication, Financial and insurance activities, and real estate activities (excluding companies). Specifically, these sectors are anticipated to experience lucrative growth. The imperative role of Romanian public governance lies in supporting these sectors, considering them as a foundational support crucial for the coexistence of others.

Observably, the forecasted scenarios exhibit minimal error deviation concerning both the upper and lower control limits. This validates the accuracy of the statistical and forecast analysis.

Indicators considered in the study:

1. Active business population - number (I1)
2. Newly established businesses - number (I2)
3. Abolition of businesses in t - number (I3)
4. Newly established enterprises in t-3 that have survived to t - number (I4)
5. Enterprises with high employment growth (increase of 10% or more) - number (I5)
6. Persons employed in enterprises active in t - number (I6)
7. Employed in enterprises active in t - number (I7)
8. Persons engaged in business established in t - number (I8)
9. Employees in businesses established in t - number (I9)
10. Persons engaged in business abolished in t - number (I10)
11. Employees in businesses dissolved in t - number (I11)
12. Persons employed in enterprises newly established in t-3 who have survived to t - number (I12)
13. Persons employed in the year of establishment in enterprises newly established in t-3 who have survived to t - number (I13)
14. Net business growth - percentage (I14)
15. Net business situation: establishment rate + dissolution rate - percentage (I15)

16. Establishment rate: number of enterprises established in the reference period (t) divided by the number of enterprises active in t - percentage (I16)
17. Dissolution rate: number of enterprises disbanded in the reference period (t) divided by the number of enterprises active in t - percentage (I17)
18. 3-year survival rate: number of enterprises in the reference period (t) newly established in t-3 that survived to t divided by the number of enterprises established in t-3 - percentage (I18)
19. Share of enterprises aged 3 years in the business population - percentage (I19)
20. Employment rate of start-ups: number of persons employed in the reference period (t) among start-ups in t, divided by the number of persons employed in t in the total number of active enterprises - percentage (I20)
21. Average size of start-ups: number of persons employed in the reference period (t) among start-ups in t, divided by the number of start-ups in t (I21)
22. Rate of new employees paid in enterprises: number of employees in the reference period (t) of newly established enterprises in t, divided by the number of persons employed in t in enterprises newly established in t - percentage (I22)
23. Employment rate in disbanded enterprises: number of persons employed in the reference period (t) within the disbanded enterprises divided by the number of persons employed in t in enterprises active in t - percentage (I23)

24. Enterprise growth rate of three years: number of persons employed in the reference period (t) in newly established enterprises in t-3, which survived to t, divided by the number of persons employed in t -3 by the same companies, a percentage growth rate - percentage (I24)

25. Employment rate of enterprises older than 3 years: number of persons employed in newly established enterprises in t-3 who survived in t, divided by the number of persons employed in active enterprises - percentage (I25)

26. Share of high-growth enterprises in employment: number of high-growth enterprises divided by the number of active enterprises with at least 10 employees - percentage (I26)

27. Share of enterprises with measured increased growth in employment: number of enterprises with increased growth divided by the number of active enterprises with at least 10 employees - percentage (I27).

Sectors covered in the study:

- Industry, construction, and services, except for insurance activities of companies (Ix);
- Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles (Ix1);
- Professional, scientific and technical activities; administrative and support activities (Ix2);
- Industry (except construction) (Ix3);

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- Constructions (Ix4);
- Transport and storage (Ix5);
- Arts, entertainment and recreation; other service activities (Ix6);
- Accommodation and food services (Ix7);
- Information and communication (Ix8);
- Education, human health and social assistance (Ix9);
- Financial and insurance activities; real estate activities, except companies (Ix10).

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PREDICTIVE ANALYSIS OF FOOD AND SERVICE-CENTRIC ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN MOUNTAINOUS REGIONS: INSIGHTS FROM AGRITOURISM

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Abstract

The manuscript provides a predictive analysis of the food and service sectors in the mountainous regions of Central and Eastern Europe. In recent times, agro-tourism has emerged as a primary solution for the agro-forestry-pastoral European system. Projections indicate that this sub-sector will play a pivotal role in the European food and service sectors. Data sourced from Eurostat was processed using Excel and SPSS, employing analytical models similar to those found in existing published papers.

Keywords: forecasting, mountain entrepreneurship, food and services, agro-tourism

The specific indicator for the population of active enterprises in mountain entrepreneurship within the food and accommodation sectors reveals noteworthy variations based on Eurostat data for Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries during the examined period. Specifically, Bulgaria experienced a 4.24% change, the Czech Republic exhibited an -11.73% shift, Croatia demonstrated a notable increase of 14.91%, Austria saw a decrease of -13.03%, Poland showed a positive shift of 5.27% (2016/2017), Romania displayed a growth of 9.61%, and Slovakia indicated a 7.94% increase. Over the period from 2008 to 2018, there was an overall rise in mountain entrepreneurship in CEE countries, and the forecasting model for 2050 suggests substantial growth in the coming years (refer to Figure 1).

Experts assert that agro-tourism will be the pivotal point of development for mountain entrepreneurship in the food and accommodation sectors. Agro-tourism, characterized as a multifaceted activity, currently represents an opportunity to enhance both human health and environmental well-being, contributing to the realization of the overarching goal of sustainability in rural areas. Presently, European entrepreneurial emphasis is placed on natural, organic, and bio products, integrating them across various human activities, encompassing health, and environment, all under the overarching

theme of sustainability. The imperative to instill sustainability in activities, health, and the environment within rural areas, particularly within the realm of agritourism, is a prevalent and actively pursued topic in contemporary discourse.

Fig. 3: Mountain entrepreneurship between 2008 and 2050 (statistic analysis and foercasting)

Source: Designed by authors according to Eurostat - Business Demography

Statistics

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The mountainous rural setting provides significant opportunities for the advancement of agrotourism, a practice deemed essential in the contemporary context. The sustainability of European agrotourism signifies an integral connection between health, the rural environment, and the economic, social, and cultural facets of the constituent community. This interconnectedness exerts a multiplier effect on all domains with which agrotourism interacts. In 2017, the number of agritourism guesthouses totaled 2556 units, with a projected increase to 7113 units by 2030. The anticipated workforce engaged in agritourism is expected to reach approximately 5409 individuals, compared to 4978 persons in 2017 (Ciolac et al., 2019).

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Evidently, the marginal difference in occupation between 2017 and 2030 is not pronounced. Consequently, within the realm of mountain entrepreneurship, the augmentation of the food and accommodation sector will not be contingent upon an upsurge in the number of individuals involved but rather on the elevation of human capital quality and the implementation of innovative initiatives in mountain rural areas.

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European nations, particularly those in Central and Eastern Europe and beyond, should perceive rural development as an opportunity to combat poverty, ensuring the enduring sustainability of rural environments. Each economic sector - primary, secondary, tertiary, and quaternary - should be incentivized to devise sustainability solutions within its specific domain. Sustainability, characterized by guiding actions responsibly and harmoniously, underscores values and principles. Agrotourism emerges as an innovative solution, involving diversification strategies where farms integrate recreational and leisure activities for tourists alongside agro-forestry-pastoral endeavors. The economic and non-economic benefits of agrotourism extend to farmers, visitors, and local communities. Presently, the sustainability of mountain entrepreneurship encompasses the integration of natural, organic, and eco-friendly elements into all facets of human activities, health, and the environment (Ciolac et al., 2019).

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FOOD AND SERVICES SECTORS IN CENTRAL AND EASTERN EUROPEAN COUNTRIES. CASE STUDY OF MOUNTAIN AREA

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Abstract

The research underscores the significance of the food and accommodation sectors within Central and Eastern European countries, with a specific focus on the mountainous regions. The study draws insights from selected European areas, specifically the Austrian Tyrol and the North-East of Romania. An examination of Eurostat indicators reveals a positive trend in entrepreneurship within the Central and Eastern European countries. This positive dynamic is often fueled by a swift desire for financial gain, sometimes at the expense of considering the contextual nuances of dietary behaviors and service provision under normal conditions. Notably, mountain entrepreneurs may, at times, prioritize expedient and unsustainable earnings over quality. The research utilizes data sourced from

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Eurostat, employing Excel and SPSS for processing, and adopts analytical models akin to those found in existing literature.

Keywords: sustainability of the mountain area; Austrian Tyrol region; North-East region of Romania; food and accommodation sectors

1. Introduction

This study focuses on the food and accommodation sector, undertaking an analysis of mountain entrepreneurship to propose solutions for the sustainability of agribusiness. Relevant Eurostat entrepreneurship indicators from Austria and select Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries, including Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, and Slovakia, are considered. The analysis spans the period 2011-2017, with specific intervals receiving due attention. Case studies involve recognized mountain products, with a detailed examination of entrepreneurship in the mountain regions of Austria, specifically Tyrol, and Romania's North-East. (Benaki et al., 2007; Blazkova et al., 2016; Pavolova et al., 2021)

2. Results and data

During the examined timeframe, the specific indicator for the food and accommodation sectors is the population of active enterprises. Notable increases in this indicator were observed in Bulgaria (3.37%), Croatia (8.92%), Lithuania (51.67%), Romania (34.52%), Slovakia (1.96%), Estonia (12.42% between 2015-2017), and Poland (5.61% between 2016-2017). Conversely, Austria experienced a decrease of -7.15%, the Czech Republic - 6.35% (between 2013-2017), Hungary -10.67% (between 2011-2017), and Latvia -0.44% (between 2016-2017) in the population of active enterprises.

The fluctuations observed in the Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries prompted a comparative investigation between two distinct European entrepreneurship types, namely Tyrol (Austria) and Northeast (Romania). Tyrol, a pivotal Austrian region for food and accommodation services, encompasses Außerfern, Innsbruck, Osttirol, Tiroler Oberland, and Tiroler Unterland. In contrast, the Northeast, an emerging region in Romania, comprises Bacau, Botosani, Iasi, Neamt, Suceava, and Vaslui. Although the Austrian population of active enterprises and their respective regions experienced a decline, specifically Tirol (-6.04%), Außerfern (-

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5.63%), Innsbruck (-6.32%), Osttirol (-10.56%), Tiroler Oberland (-2.23%), and Tiroler Unterland (-8.14%), Romanian regions and counties witnessed an increase in the population of active enterprises: North-East (87.77%), Bacau (53.60%), Botosani (105.67%), Iasi (68.45%), Neamt (81.41%), Suceava (120.74%), and Vaslui (117.55%). Similar trends were observed in other CEE countries.

Considering the benefits of mountain products, entrepreneurs are encouraged to develop businesses in mountainous regions. Over the analyzed period, the CEE countries with the highest growth in entrepreneurship within the accommodation and food services sector were the Czech Republic (58085 units in 2017), Poland (82147 units in 2017), and Romania (37926 units in 2017). The population of active enterprises in t – number fluctuated in the period 2013-2018 in Austria (-11.54%), Bulgaria (3.26%), Czech Republic (-5.13%), Estonia (25.33%), Croatia (17.95%), Hungary (2.18%), Lithuania (35.99%), Latvia (18.21%), Poland (-13.87%), Romania (10.22%), and Slovakia (9.40%). These CEE countries exhibited considerable and noteworthy fluctuations or linearity in this context (figure 1). The extent of this growth's sustainability remains uncertain, with some studies suggesting that it might involve increased consumption of high-fat or artificially grown foods, potentially compromising quality.

Fig. 1: Population of active enterprises in CEE countries (Accommodation and food services sectors)

Source: Designed by authors according to Eurostat - Business Demography Statistics

Despite Austria showcasing a marginal decline in the population of active enterprises index during the 2008-2017 period, it still serves as a benchmark for the Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries (figure 2).

Fig. 2: Population of active enterprises in Austria and Romania, respectively
Austrian Tyrol and Romanian North-East (Accommodation and food
services sectors)

Source: Designed by authors according to Eurostat - Business Demography
Statistics

Austria, surrounded by Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries, serves as a model for other economies due to its provision of higher-quality services and food behaviors. The Austrian population of active enterprises experienced a decrease from 2008 to 2017, declining by -4130 units (from 57726 units to 53596). In contrast, the Romanian population of active enterprises saw an increase from 2011 to 2017, growing by 9732 units (from 28194 units to 37926). This trend was similarly observed in Tyrol, the region with the highest mountain potential in Austria, although the intensity of the decrease varied. Specifically, the population of active enterprises in Tyrol declined by -688 units (from 11394 units to 10706). Conversely, in the North-East region of Romania, the degree of entrepreneurship increased by 2469 units (from 2813 units to 5282).

3. Conclusion

The selected mountain products and regions stand as representative examples for Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries. Within this framework, the authors posit that mountain entrepreneurship presents viable solutions for sustainable growth. As previously articulated, the authors assert that a comparative analysis between Austrian Tyrol and the North-East region of Romania is warranted due to shared geographical features (mountainous regions and predominantly rural areas) and comparable socio-economic conditions. The entrepreneurial landscapes in these two countries and regions exhibit noteworthy parallels.

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ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN ENTREPRENEURS OF DAIRY AND BEEKEEPING PRODUCTS: A BIOTIC PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

The manuscript introduces Romanian entrepreneurs engaged in the production of probiotic-rich dairy and beekeeping products within mountainous regions. Probiotic experts affirm the probiotic efficacy of certain dairy and beekeeping items. The document showcases mountain-based producers specializing in fermented dairy products such as yogurt, sana, and kefir, as well as natural honey variants including honeydew (manna), mountain polyflora, coniferous, acacia, and chestnut.

Keywords: beekeeping producers, dairy producers, mountain entrepreneurship

M.C. – conceptualization; B.C. – conceptualization and final

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Introduction:

Nestled within the breathtaking landscapes of Romania's mountains, a harmonious symphony of entrepreneurial endeavors unfolds, led by resilient individuals who delve into the realms of dairy and beekeeping. This article explores the unique and biotically enriched ventures undertaken by Romanian mountain entrepreneurs, shedding light on the symbiotic relationship between these entrepreneurs, nature, and the products they cultivate.

The Biotic Symphony of Dairy:

In the high-altitude pastures of Romania's mountainous regions, a biotic symphony unfolds as local entrepreneurs engage in the production of dairy products. Beyond the ordinary, these producers infuse their artisanal creations with probiotic richness. Yogurt, sana, and kefir, the staples of Romanian dairy craftsmanship, transcend their traditional roles, becoming not only sources of nutrition but also carriers of beneficial biota.

The fermentation process, a key aspect of these dairy productions, introduces live cultures that contribute to the biotic diversity of the final products. Romanian mountain entrepreneurs take pride in their commitment to preserving local biodiversity and crafting dairy delights that go beyond the ordinary, contributing to the broader narrative of biotic sustenance.

Beekeeping Bliss and Biotic Diversity:

In perfect synergy with their dairy counterparts, Romanian mountain beekeepers engage in the art of apiculture, producing honey that reflects the biotic diversity of the region. Beekeeping practices become a biotic dance, where bees play a crucial role in pollination, fostering the flourishing diversity of mountain flora.

The resulting honey varieties, including honeydew (manna), mountain polyflora, coniferous, acacia, and chestnut, each embody a distinct biotic profile. The geographical and ecological characteristics of the mountains imprint unique flavors and potential probiotic benefits, making these honey varieties not just sweet delights but also carriers of the mountain's biotic essence.

Sustainability in Harmony with Biotic Balance:

Romanian mountain entrepreneurs, custodians of their natural surroundings, understand the delicate equilibrium needed for sustainable practices. The biotic richness of the mountains is not only harnessed but also preserved through eco-conscious approaches. Sustainable beekeeping and dairy production practices contribute to maintaining the biotic balance, ensuring that nature and entrepreneurship coexist harmoniously.

Biotic Innovation and Tradition:

Beyond the economic facets of their endeavors, Romanian mountain entrepreneurs infuse their dairy and beekeeping practices with innovative biotic elements. Probiotics, known for their potential health benefits, become a bridge between tradition and modern wellness trends. These entrepreneurs are at the forefront of biotic innovation, tapping into the growing consumer preference for products that nourish both the body and the surrounding ecosystem.

Conclusion:

Romanian mountain entrepreneurs of dairy and beekeeping products emerge not just as business leaders but as stewards of the biotic richness that defines their landscape. Their commitment to sustainability, biotic innovation, and the preservation of local biodiversity showcases a holistic approach to entrepreneurship. As they continue to cultivate dairy and beekeeping products that resonate with a biotic symphony, these entrepreneurs not only contribute to local economies but also stand as champions of a harmonious coexistence between nature and business.

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ADO – SC Ferma Denis SRL

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Figura A1. Cutie Iaurt ADO 2,8% de cantitate 170 g - lot 1031 (expiră pe 14.10.2021)

Figura A2. Analize fizico-chimice, Iaurt ADO 2,8%

Figura A3. Cutie Iaurt 10% de cantitate 1 Kg – lot 1049 (expiră pe 19.10.2021); analize fizico-chimice

Figura A4. Sticlă Chefir 3,3% de cantitate 0,5 l – lot 1077 (expiră pe 27.10.2021); analize fizico-chimice

Figura A5. Magazin ADO

Figura A6. Produse ADO

Figura A7. Fermă ADO

Figura A8. Produse probiotice ADO

Figura A8. Produse ADO

Figura A9. Magazin ADO

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Gordon

Figura G1. Compania Gordon

Figura G2. Fermă Gordon

Figura G3. Hală Gordon

Figura G4. Ferma Gordon

Figura G5. Produse probiotice Gordon

Figura G6. Produse Gordon

Figura G7. Produse Gordon

Figura G8. Munții Harghita, zona Gordon

← → ↻ aucthan.ro/store/laurt-Gordon-900-g/p/293126# 🔍 ☆ ⚙️ 📄 B ⋮

CARACTERISTICI PRODUS

Produsul se obtine din lapte pasteurizat, standardizat la 2.8% si insamantat cu cultura termofila.

INFORMATII NUTRITIONALE		INGREDIENTE SI ALERGENI	
kJ pe 100g sau 100ml	227	Ingrediente	Lapte de vaca pasteurizat, culturi lactice selectate.
kcal pe 100g sau 100ml	54	Alergeni descriere	Lactoza
Grasimi (g sau ml)	2.8		
din care acizi grasi saturati (g sau ml)	1.86		
Glucide (g sau ml)	4.05		
din care zaharuri (g sau ml)	2.29		
Sare (g sau m)	0.32		
Proteine (g sau ml)	3.2		

Feedback

Figura G9. Proprietăți nutriționale și fizico-chimice Iaurt Gordon 2,8%

Sana Gordon 3.6 % grăsime
Greutate: 330g PET

Informații nutriționale medii
per 100g

valoare energetică în kJ și kcal
275 kJ / 66 kcal

grăsimi, g
3.6 g

- din care: acizi grași saturați, g
2.41 g

glucide, g
4.62 g

- din care: zaharuri, g
2.39 g

proteine, g
3.75 g

sare, g
0.32g

Figura G10. Proprietăți nutriționale și fizico-chimice Sana Gordon 3,6%

Kefir Gordon 3.5 % grăsimi	
Greutate: 330g PET	
Informații nutriționale medii	
per 100g	
valoare energetică în kJ și kcal	
	275 kJ / 66 kcal
grăsimi, g	3.50g
- din care: acizi grași saturați, g	2.27 g
glucide, g	4.93 g
- din care: zaharuri, g	2.82 g
proteine, g	3.65 g
sare, g	0.12 g

Figura G11. Proprietăți nutriționale și fizico-chimice Kefir Gordon 3,5%

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Popa Tudor Ionuț PFA

Figura PTI1. Stupi Popa Tudor Ionuț PFA

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Figura PTI2. Stupi Popa Tudor Ionuț PFA

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Figura PTI3. Stupi Popa Tudor Ionuț PFA

Figura PTI4. Stupi Popa Tudor Ionuț PFA

Figura PTI5. Produse Popa Tudor Ionuț PFA

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Radu Ion PFA

Figura R1. Stupi și stupine Radu Ion PFA

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Figura R2. Albine din familiile apicole Radu Ion PFA

Figura R3. Laborator Radu Ion PFA

Figura R4. Laborator Radu Ion PFA

Figura R5. Stupi Radu Ion PFA

Figura R6. Miere de salcâm / polifloră de munte

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Figura R7. Miere de mană

Figura R3. Arealul montan Masivul Ivănețu

Figura R4. Trovanți din Munții Buzăului

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Figura V1. Miere de mană / munte Vinereanu

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Figura V2. Stupina Vaideeni

Figura V3. Areal montan Vaideeni

Figura V4. Areal montan Vaideeni

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